

NEW INSCRIPTIONS FROM HADRIANOI PROS OLYMPON (MYSIA)

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ABSTRACT

During our museum research in Bithynia in 2010, a visit to Orhaneli (Hadrianoi) under the supervision of Enver Sağır, the director of the Bursa Archaeological Museum, enabled us to work on a group of pieces registered in the inventory records of the museum and placed in the garden of the county-council of Orhaneli. The pieces were gathered from nearby settlements and taken into protection in the garden. Five of these pieces, which are inscribed, will be analysed in detail epigraphically, while the other un-inscribed ones are mentioned superficially. These inscriptions have different information. No. 1 is a honourification of emperor Antoninus Pius by three strategs. Nr. 2 has already been published, and contains the epigram of Iulia Hagne. Nr. 3 is the funerary inscription of Diostratos and Aphia, whom their sons commemorated. Nr. 4 contains a funerary inscription of Aurelius Agapetos, who was a Christian and built the grave for himself, his child and grandchildren. No. 5 is probably a partial inscription of a building constructed after an oracle. Apart from inscriptions there are many pieces, amongst which an osthok, building stones of a church, a pithos with the sign of cross and an altar are the most noteworthy.

Keywords: Orhaneli, Hadrianoi pros Olympon, Mysia, Olympene, Inscriptions, Bithynia.

ÖZET

Hadrianoi Pros Olympon'dan (Mysia) Yeni Yazıtlar

2010 yılı Bithynia müze arařtırmalarımız esnasında, Bursa Arkeoloji Müzesi müdürü Sayın Enver Sağır'ın eřlięinde Orhaneli'ne yaptığımız bir ziyaret neticesinde, belediye binasının önünde toplanmış ve müze envanterine kayıtlı, arasında yazıtların da bulunduęu bir grup eser arařtırma planımıza dâhil olmuştur. Yakın çevreden getirilerek korunmaya alınmış olan bu eserler grup olarak bu makalede incelenecektir. Eserlerden beş tanesi yazıtlıdır. Yazıt taşımayan eserlere de bilgi amaçlı bu makalede kısaca değinilecektir. 1 no'lu yazıt imparator Antoninus

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Pius'un üç strategos tarafından onurlandırılmasını içermektedir. 2 no'lu yazıt daha önce yayınlanmış olup, Iulia Hagne'nin mezar epigramını içermektedir. 3 no'lu yazıt Diostratos ve Aphia'nın çocukları tarafından dikilen mezar taşı; 4 no'lu yazıt da, Hıristiyan olan Aurelius Agapetos'un yaşarken kendisi, çocuğu ve torunları için yaptırdığı mezarın yazıtıdır. 5 no'lu yazıt ise olasılıkla bir kehanet sonrası yapılan bir binanın yazıtının küçük bir kısmı niteliğindedir. Belediye binasının önünde bu yazıtlarla beraber pek çok eser bulunmakla birlikte, bir ostotek, bir kiliseye ait yapı taşları, üzerinde haç işlenmesi olan bir pithos ve bir altar en dikkat çekenleridir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Orhaneli, Hadrianoi pros Olympon, Mysia, Olympene, Yazıtlar, Bithynia

Orhaneli (Hadrianoi) is a county, 33 km south of Bursa. It was in Antiquity in the region of "Olympene" within the borders of Mysia (see fig. 12 and 13)¹. The Region of Mysia Olympene was bounded by Prusa ad Olympon, a Bithynian city, to the North; Hellespontine Phrygia (Phrygia Epiktetos) to the South; Mount Olympos (Uludağ) to the East; and the region of Mysia Abrettene, the cities of Apollonia ad Rhyndacum (Ulubat) and Miletupolis (Mustafakemalpaşa) to the West². The name of Hadrianoi, the ancient name of Orhaneli, is preserved in the name Adranos that was used for Orhaneli until the early 20th century. The city of Hadrianoi that is also attested in the inscriptions³ was named after emperor Hadrianus, who founded the city in A.D. 131/2⁴. There is no evidence from literary sources concerning Hadrianoi until Byzantine Period. In the acts of Concilia Oecumenica, it is recorded that Bishop David from Hadrianoi attended the council of Calchedon in A.D. 451 and Bishop Helios from Hadrianoi the synod of Constantinople and Jerusalem in A.D. 536⁵. Hierokles lists the city under Bithynia of Eparkheia Pontike⁶. In the Notitiae Episcopatum,

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² I. Hadr., 133-134.

³ I. Hadr., nos. 12, 17, 45, 52; I. Prus. no.18.

⁴ I. Hadr. 157; Boatwright 2000, 189.

⁵ ACO, *Conc.Chalc.451* 2.1.1 61.20, 2.1.2 74.31, 2.1.2 89.11, 2.1.2 135.17, 2.1.2 147.24 and 2.1.3 93.23; ACO, *Syn.Cons.Hier.536* 3.127. 22, 3.155.42, 3.161.40 and 3.170.17.

⁶ Hierokles 693, 5.

Hadrianoi was subject to the bishopric of Nikomedeia under Eparkheia Bithynia⁷.

Various travellers and scholars visited or conducted investigations in and around the city from the beginning of the 20th century⁸. They copied inscriptions and recorded several ancient buildings most of which seems to have since been destroyed. The last comprehensive geographical and epigraphic research was conducted between 1979 – 1983 by Elmar Schwertheim, who published the results of his research in *Die Inschriften von Hadrianoi und Hadrianeia* (here “I.Hadr.”) in 1987.

In recent years some ancient stones were collected in the garden of the county-council of Orhaneli. Five of these pieces are inscribed and one of these inscriptions has already been published (No. 2; figs. 2 a-b) by E. Schwertheim.

No. 1) Strategs Pollion, Diodoros and Hermokles honour Antoninus Pius (Fig. 1 a-b).

F.P.: Orhaneli (Bursa); Inv. No.: 34. Profiled marble statue base; broken at its right-front-up; back side left rough; dowel hole at the top; The remaining part of the inscription on the front face is well-preserved.

H.: 130 cm; L.: 54 cm; D.: 67 cm; Lh.: 2,5 cm.

	[Ϝ Ἀγαθ]ῆι Τύχηι Ϝ	<i>With Good Fortune!</i>
2	[Αὐτοκρ]άτορα Καίσαρα Τ(ίτον) Αἴλιον	<i>Pollion, son of [..]nophanes,</i>
	[Ἀδριανὸν] ἂν Ἀντωνεῖνον Σεβ(αστὸν) Ϝ	<i>Diodoros, son of [Eu]boulos and</i>
4	[Εὐσεβῆ], θεοῦ Ἀδριανοῦ υἱόν,	<i>Hermokles, son of Gly[k]on, who</i>
	[θεοῦ] Τραιανοῦ Παρθικοῦ υἱό-	<i>have been strategs, erected from</i>
6	[νόν], θεοῦ Νέρουα ἔκγονον,	<i>the city revenues (this statue of)</i>
	[ἀρχι]ερέα μέγιστον, δημαρ-	<i>Imperator Caesar Titus Aelius</i>
8	[χικ]ῆς ἐξουσίας τὸ γ', ὕπατον	<i>Hadrianus Antoninus Augustus</i>
	[τὸ γ', πα]τέρα πατρίδος, Πωλλίωv	<i>[Pius], the son of God Hadrianus,</i>
10	[. .]νοφάνουσι καὶ Διόδωρος	<i>the grandson of [God] Traianus</i>
	[Εὐ]βούλου καὶ Ἑρμόκλης Γλύ-	<i>Parthicus, grand-grandson of God</i>
12	[κ]ῶνος στρατηγήσαντες ἐ[κ]	<i>Nerva, Pontifex Maximus, Trib. Pot.</i>
	[τ]ων τῆς πόλεως χρημάτων	<i>III, Cos. [III], father of the Country.</i>
14	Ϝ ἀνέστησαν. Ϝ	

⁷ Not. Ep. 2.7.199, 3.8.235, 4.7.188, 7.7.227, 9.7.125, 10.7.142, 13.7.138.

⁸ Hamilton 1842, 90-94; Le Bas 1845, 203-213; Perrot et al. 1872, 61-68; Texier 1882, 142-144; Munro – Anthony 1897, 265-266; Mordtmann 1925, 309-312.

L. 8-9: Trib. Pot. III and Cos. [III], Antoninus Pius, A.D. 139-140.

L. 10: [.]νοφάνους: see *LGPN V.A*, 306 for the name of Μηνοφάνης frequently used in Asia Minor; for other possibilities of Ξενοφάνης see *LGPN V.A*, 342 and of Ζηνοφάνης see *LGPN V.A*, 191.

At the bottom section, there are some letters, which cannot be understood and are probably a later carving, as OY OY (see fig. 1b).

Pollion, Diodoros and Hermokles, who honoured Antoninus Pius, were qualified as στρατηγήσαντες. During the Roman Imperial Period, strategs (στρατηγοί), who undertook public security in towns and countryside, were responsible for the police organization in several cities of Asia Minor⁹. In addition to the function of urban and regional security, they could also hold political and juridical duties¹⁰. Strategs were able to give petition for honourifications; to construct public buildings and to erect statues¹¹. For instance, another inscription from Hadrianoi reads that Attinas honoured L. Aelius Caesar, adoptive son of Hadrianus, and erected his statue in his honour in A.D. 137 during his strategship¹².

No. 2) Funerary Epigram of Iulia Hagne (Figs. 2 a-b)

F.P.: Serçeler (Orhaneli); Inv. No. 6; Funerary stele; Publication: I. Hadr. 76; Merkelbach – Stauber 2001, 12, no. 08/08/09.

H.: 135 cm; L.: 61 cm; T.: 26 cm; Lh.: 2,5 cm.

⁹ Liebenam 1900, 286-288; Reid 1913, 463-464; Magie 1950, I 643-644; Mason 1974, 161-162; Brélaz 2005, 74-87; Dimitriev 2005, 128-129. For this sort of στρατηγοί within the borders of the Roman Empire see Liebenam 1900, 558-564; Στρατηγοί could be στεφανηφόρος, πρυτανεύς, γραμματεύς and δεκάπρωτος at the same time (Dimitriev 2005, 227). The number of strategs was usually 5, but sometimes they could be 3 or 4 and this office created its inner hierarchy by the end of 2nd century, later the head was called πρώτος στρατηγός (Magie 1950, I 643-644). From early in the 3rd century, the titles στρατηγός and ειρηνάρχος were held by the same person (Dimitriev 2005, 281-282). For στρατηγός ἐπὶ τῆς χώρας, στρατηγός ἐπὶ τῆς ειρήνης, ειρηνάρχος, νυκτοστράτηγος see Liebenam 1900, 288, fn. 8; Magie 1950, I 644; Dimitriev 2005, 206-213; Feld 2005, 181; Brélaz 2005, Chapter III (esp. for *strategoï*, 74-87). The usage of this office in inscriptions sometimes together with λυκιάρχης lead scholars to consider that it was an office connected with the lyciarchate (Balland 1981, 242-243, no. 76), another similar connection was established with ἀρχιφυλαξ (Kokkinia 2000, 221-222).

¹⁰ Brélaz 2005, 74.

¹¹ Dimitriev 2005, 128-129.

¹² Hamilton 1842, II 399; Le Bas 1845, 207-208; LBW no. 1053; Homolle 1893, 637-638, no.3; IGR III 35 = MAMA IV 240; I. Hadr., 37, no. 43: Λ. Αἴλιον Καίσαρα | Αὐτοκράτορος Ἀδριανοῦ Σεβαστοῦ υἱὸν | θεοῦ Τραϊανοῦ υἱωνὸν | θεοῦ Νέρουα ἔκγονον | δημαρχικῆς ἐξουσίας | ὑπάτων τὸ β', Ἀττινᾶς | Γλύκωνος στρατηγῶν ἐκ τῶν ἰδίων ἀνέστησεν.

- | | | |
|----|---|--|
| 2 | Ἰουλία Ἄγνη
Ἀπολλωνιάτις
πολλά ἀποδημήσασα
θεὸν πάτριον προλιποῦσα
Θερμηνῶν γαίης, ἣν
Μοῖρα πάτραν ἐπέκλωσεν
ψυχῆς ἐκιτταμένης
ἄλαλον δέμας ἐνθάδε
κείμεαι. | <i>Iulia Hagne from Apollonia (ad Rhyndacum).
I, who have been far away (from home) leaving the ancestral god of the Thermenians' land that Fate endowed (me) as (my) fatherland, lie here as an unspeaking body, after (my) soul flew away.</i> |
| 10 | συμβίῳ γλυκυτάτῃ Οὐρσου-
λος ἐποίησεν. | <i>Ursulus prepared (this grave) for his dearest spouse.</i> |

L.7: ἐκιτταμένης = ἐξισταμένης (Schwertheim)

The origin of Iulia Hagne, a Roman citizen, was a place called Therma¹³ within the territory of Apollonia ad Rhyndacum¹⁴ (Ulubat/Apolyont). The inscription containing an epigram between the lines 3-7 was dated to the 1st century B.C. by Schwertheim¹⁵. But, the ligatures, the typeface (e.g. omega and sigma) don't seem to support this (see fig 2b), so the inscription should be dated to a later period, as Merkelbach and Stauber indicated¹⁶.

No. 3) Funerary Altar of Diostratos and Aphia (Figs. 3 a-b)

F.P.: Orhaneli (Bursa); Inv. No. 13; Marble funerary altar; Upper section damaged; bottom profiled; an inscription of 7 lines, the first of which is poorly preserved.

H.: 81 cm; L.: 32 cm; D.: 53 cm; Lh.: 3,5-4 cm.

- | | | |
|---|--------------------------------------|---|
| | [~Ε]τους [.]πα' μη[v]- | <i>In the month of</i> |
| 2 | ὄς Δύστρου· Διό-
δωρος καὶ Μενέφ- | <i>Dystros of the year -81.
Diodoros and</i> |
| 4 | ρων Διοστράτω
τῷ πατρὶ καὶ Ἀφ[ί]- | <i>Menephron, for (their)
father Diostratos and</i> |
| 6 | α τῆ μητρὶ μνήμ-
ης χάριν. | <i>mother Aphia, in (their)
memory.</i> |

¹³ Merkelbach – Stauber (2001, 12) suggests that Θερμηνοὶ were the inhabitants of Therma Basilika near Prusa.

¹⁴ Robert 1980, 93-98; Abmeier 1990, 1-16; DNP 1, p. 871, s.v. Apollonia [6]; Barrington Atlas Map. 52-D4 and p. 786

¹⁵ I. Hadr., 57-58

¹⁶ Merkelbach – Stauber 2001, 12.

L.1, [.]πα', -81: Sullan Era. Though the first letter of the number cannot be read completely, a half vertical stroke can be seen at the bottom of the line. This suggests five letters which might have been carved representing hundreds: P (100), T (300), Y (400), Φ (500) and Ψ (700). The number Ψ should be eliminated, since the year we obtain reaches a period when the Sullan Era had ended (781 = A.D. 696/7). The number Φ takes us to the year A.D. 496/7, when we can still find examples dated in the Sullan Era¹⁷. The number Y provides A.D. 396/7, while T gives A.D. 296/7, which are more probable years. In general, the typeface suggests a date within or later than 2nd century, considering the omega shaped in minuscule form, the sigma with corners and the delta with its left stroke carved longer. But, since some of the 1st and 2nd century A.D. inscriptions from Hadrianoi carry similar typefaces¹⁸, the number P is also possible, and then the year becomes A.D. 96/7. Finally, the dating of the inscription seems to be in the month of Dystros¹⁹ of the several years mentioned above, perhaps A.D. 96/7.

L.5. Ἀφία is a personal name often attested in western Asia Minor. See Pape – Benseler 180; Zgusta 1964, 81, § 66-39; LGPN V.A., 92.

No. 4) The Gravestone of Aurelius Agapetos (Figs. 4 a-b)

Marble grave stone; lower section missing; profiled at top and decorated with acroteria around the pediment; in the middle of the pediment is a rosette. F.P.: Orhaneli (Bursa); Inv. No. 19.

H.: 56 cm; L.: 32 cm; D.: 35 cm; Lh.: 2,5-2 cm.

Αὐρήλιος Ἀγκάπητος	<i>Aurelius Agapetos</i>
2 ἐαυτῷ ζῶν καὶ τέκν[ω]	<i>constructed this</i>
καὶ τέκνου τέκν-	<i>burial place,</i>
4 οἱς κατεσ- [[/////]]	<i>while alive, for himself,</i>
κεύασεν κοιμητήρι-	<i>(his) child and children of (his) child.</i>
6 ον ἐν ὀνόματι Χρῆστ[του]	<i>In the name of Christ ...</i>
γέγραπτα[ι ----- 9-10 -----]	<i>.. (as was?) prescribed ...</i>
8 ΟΟΥΓΟ[----- 13-14 ----]	-----
ΕΓ[----- 17-18 -----]	-----

¹⁷ MAMA IV 225 = Foss 1977, 285 (A.D. 585); Drew-Bear 1978, 111, no. 50 (A.D. 563); Leschhorn 1993, 423.

¹⁸ For instance I. Hadr. 24 has similar letter features and was dated to the end of A.D. 1st century.

¹⁹ For the month of Dystros (24 January-21 February) see Samuel 1972, 182; Hannah 2005, 133-135.

fulfilled following an oracle given by propheteus²⁵. This inscription is not from an altar or a statue base, but probably a building fragment placed on top of a structure (e.g. a lintel). The oracle would most probably have been given in the temple of Zeus Kersoullos located near the villages of Belenören and Akçapınar²⁶.

Apart from these inscriptions, there are many ancient large and small pieces in the garden of the county-council. Amongst which, an ostothek with akroteria on its lid (fig. 6 a-c), building stones from a church including a stone with a large cross (figs. 7 a-b and 11), an unglazed pottery pithos²⁷ with the sign of the cross and other moulded relief-work (figs. 8 a-b and 9) and an un-inscribed altar (fig. 10) are amongst the most noteworthy items.

Personal Names

Ἀγάπητος	3	Ἑρμόκλης	1
Ἀυρήλιος	3	[Εὔ]βουλος	1
Ἀφία	2	Μενέφρων	2
Γλύκων	1	Πωλλίων	1
Διόδωρος	1, 2	[..]νοφάνης	1
Διόστρατος	3		

²⁵ I. Hadr., 9.

²⁶ I. Hadr. 139 and 156; see also Şahin 2001, 76-77.

²⁷ For the samples of similar pithoi inscribed or with rosetta see Yaraş 2010.

Bibliography and Abbreviations

ACO	Acta Concilia Oecumenica
AMS	Asia Minor Studien
BCH	Bulletin de Correspondance Hellénique
CIG	Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum
DNP	Der Neue Pauly
I. Nik.	IK 9 – 10: Katalog der antiken Inschriften des Museums von Iznik (Nikaia). 2 vols. S. Şahin (ed.), Bonn, Vol I: 1979 - Vol II,1: 1981 - Vol II,2 1982 - Vol II,3 1987.
I. Smyr.	IK 23 – 24: Die Inschriften von Smyrna I-III, G. Petzl (ed.), Bonn 1982-1990.
I. Eph.	IK 11,1 – 17,4: Die Inschriften von Ephesos, R. Merkelbach vd. (edd.), Bonn 1979-1981.
I. Hadr.	IK 33: Die Inschriften von Hadrianoi und Hadrianeia, E. Schwertheim (ed.), Bonn. 1987.
I. Lyk.	Die kaiserzeitlichen Inschriften Lykaoniens, fasc. 1. [Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Philosophisch-historische Klasse, Denkschriften (DAW), 232]. [Ergänzungsbände zu den Tituli Asiae Minoris 15], G. Laminger-Pascher (ed.) Vienna 1992.
I. Prus.	IK 39-40: Die Inschriften von Prusa ad Olympon. 2 vols., T. Corsten (ed.), Bonn Vol I:1991 – Vol.II: 1993.
IGR	Inscriptiones Graecae ad Res Romanas Pertinentes.
IK	Inschriften griechischer Städte aus Kleinasien.
LBW	Inscriptions Grecques et Latines recueillies en Asie Mineure I-II, P. Le Bas – W. H. Waddington (edd.), Paris 1870.
LGPN	Lexicon of Greek Personal Names.
MAMA	Monumenta Asiae Minoris Antiqua.
Pape – Benseler	Pape, W. – Benseler, G., Wörterbuch der griechischen Eigennamen, Graz 1959.
SEG	Supplementum Epigraphicum Graecum.
St. Pont. III	Recueil des inscriptions grecques et latines du Pont et de l'Arménie. Fasc. 1, J. G. C. Anderson – F. Cumont – H. Grégoire (edd.), Brussels 1910.
TIB	Tabula Imperii Byzantini.
Abmeier 1990	Abmeier, A., Zur Geschichte von Apollonia am Rhyndakos. in: Elmar Schwertheim (ed.): Mysische Studien (AMS 1) Bonn, 1-16.
Balland 1981	Balland, A., Fouilles de Xanthos. Tome VII: Inscriptions D'époque Imperiale du Létôon, Paris.

- Bean – Mitford 1970 Bean, G. E. – Mitford, T. B., *Journeys in Rough Cilicia 1964-1968*. [Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Philosophisch-historische Klasse, Denkschriften (DAW) 102]. [Ergänzungsbände zu den *Tituli Asiae Minoris* 3], Vienna.
- Boatwright 2000 Boatwright, M. T., *Hadrian and The Cities of Roman Empire*, Princeton – Oxford.
- Brélaz 2005 Brélaz, C., *La sécurité publique en Asie Mineure sous le Principat (Ier–IIIème s.ap. J.–C.)*, Basel
- Dimitriev 2005 Dimitriev, S., *City Government in Hellenistic and Roman Asia Minor*, Oxford - New York.
- Drew-Bear 1978 Drew-Bear, T., *Nouvelles Inscriptions de Phrygie*, Zutphen.
- Feld 2005 Feld, K., *Barbarische Bürger. Die Isaurier und das Römische Reich*, Berlin - New York.
- Foss 1977 Foss, C., “Two Inscriptions Attributed to the Seventh Century A.D.”, *ZPE* 25, 281-288.
- Grégoire 1922 Grégoire, H., *Recueil des Inscriptions Grecques Chretiennes d’Asie Mineure I*, Paris.
- Hamilton 1842 Hamilton, W. J., *Researches in Asia Minor, Pontus and Armenia: with some account of their antiquities and geology*, 2 Vols., London.
- Hannah 2005 Hannah, R., *Greek and Roman Calendars: Constructions of Time in the Classical World*, London.
- Homolle 1893 Homolle, T., “Nouvelles et correspondance”, *BCH* 17, 624-641.
- Kokkinia 2000 Kokkinia, C., *Die Opramoas-Inschrift von Rhodiapolis. Euergetismus und soziale Elite in Lykien*, Bonn.
- Le Bas 1845 Le Bas, P., “Voyage en Asie-Mineure. Deuxieme Rapport. Hadriani ad Olympum – Poemamenus – Blandos – Synaos – Ancyra Sinai”, *Rev. Phil* 1, 201-228.
- Leschhorn 1993 Leschhorn, W., *Antike Ären: Zeitrechnung, Politik und Geschichte im Schwarzmeerraum und in Kleinasien nördlich des Tauros*, Stuttgart.
- Liebenam 1900 Liebenam, W., *Städteverwaltung im Römischen Kaiserreiche*, Amsterdam.
- Magie 1950 Magie, D., *Roman Rule in Asia Minor to the End of the Third Century After Christ*. Vols. I - II., Princeton.
- Mason 1974 Mason, H. J., *Greek Terms for Roman Institutions: A Lexicon and Analysis*, Toronto.
- Merkelbach – Stauber 2001 Merkelbach, R. – Stauber, J., *Steinepigramme aus dem griechischen Osten*. 2. Die Nordküste Kleinasien, München – Leipzig.

- Mordtmann 1925 Mordtmann, A. D., *Anatolien. Skizzen und Reisebriefe aus Kleinasien (1850-1859)*, eingeleitet und mit Anmerkungen versehen von Franz Babinger, Hannover.
- Munro – Anthony 1897 Munro, J. A. R. – Anthony, H. M., “Explorations in Mysia”, *The Geographical Journal* 9/3, 256-276.
- Perrot et al. 1872 Perrot, G., – Guillame, E., – Delbet, E. P. J., *Exploration archéologique de la Galatie et de la Bithynie, d’une partie de la Mysie, de la Phrygie, de la Cappadoce et du Pont*, Paris.
- Petersen – Luschan 1889 Petersen, E. A. H. – Luschan, F., *Reisen im südwestlichen Kleinasien. Vol. II, Reisen in Lykien, Milyas und Kibyratis*, Vienna.
- Ramsay 1895 Ramsay, W. M., *The Cities and Bishoprics of Phrygia, Being an Essay of the Local History of Phrygia from the Earliest Times to the Turkish Conquest. Vol. I, Parts I-II.*, Oxford.
- Reid 1913 Reid, J. S., *The municipalities of the Roman empire*, Cambridge.
- Robert 1980 Robert, L., *A travers l’asie mineure: poètes et prosateurs, monnaies grecques, voyageurs et géographie*, Paris.
- Samuel 1972 Samuel A. E., *Greek and Roman chronology: calendars and years in classical antiquity*, München.
- Sterrett 1888 Sterrett, J. R. S., *The Wolfe Expeditions to Asia Minor. Papers of the American School of Classical Studies at Athens Volume III, 1884-1885*, Boston.
- Şahin 2001 Şahin, N., *Zeus’un Anadolu Kültleri*, İstanbul.
- Texier 1882 Texier, C., *Asie Mineure, Description Géographique, Historique et Archéologique des Provinces et des Villes de la Chersonnèse d’Asie*, Paris.
- Waelkens 1986 Waelkens, M., *Die kleinasiatischen Türsteine: typologische und epigraphische Untersuchungen der kleinasiatischen Grabreliefs mit Scheintür*, Mainz am Rhein.
- Yaraş 2010 Yaraş, A., *Sağlık Merkezi Allianoi’dan Yeni bir İlaç*, *Arkeoloji ve Sanat* 134, 97-104.
- Zgusta 1964 Zgusta, L., *Kleinasiatische Personennamen*, Prag.

Fig. 1a

Fig. 1b

Fig. 2a

Fig. 2b

Fig. 3a

Fig. 3b

Fig. 4a

Fig. 4b

Fig. 5

Fig. 6a

Fig. 6b

Fig. 6c

Fig. 7a

Fig. 7b

Fig. 8a

Fig. 8b

Fig. 9

Fig. 10

Fig. 11

Fig. 12 Orhaneli and its territory (by E. Schwertheim, in I. Hadr.)

